

Preparative and Structural Studies on Bimetallic Tetradithiocarbamates of Some Bivalent 3d-Metal Ions

R. C. AGGARWAL*, B. SINGH and M. K. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Some novel bimetallic tetradithiocarbamates, $MCd(Dtc)_4$, $M=VO(IV)$, $Mn(II)$, $Fe(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$, $Cu(II)$ or $Zn(II)$; Dtc =piperidine dithiocarbamate (pDtc) or diethyldithiocarbamate (Et_2Dtc), have been prepared for the first time and characterised on the basis of analytical data, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, electronic, esr and infrared spectral measurements. Tetrahedral coordination around $Zn(II)$ and $Cd(II)$, square pyramidal coordination around $VO(IV)$ and square planar coordination around $Mn(II)$, $Fe(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$ and $Cu(II)$ have been proposed in bimetallic tetradithiocarbamates

ALTHOUGH an extensive literature¹⁻⁹ is available on synthesis and structural characterisation of transition metal(II) dithiocarbamates, there is no previous work on bimetallic tetradithiocarbamates. A preparative and structural study of $MM'(Dtc)_4$ [$M'=Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$ or $Hg(II)$; $M=VO(IV)$, $Mn(II)$, $Fe(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$, $Cu(II)$ or $Zn(II)$; Dtc =dimethyl, diethyl, dibutyl, diisopropyl, piperidinyldithiocarbamate] and their complexes with Lewis bases containing one or more donor atoms such as nitrogen, oxygen, sulphur and phosphorus was undertaken and the present paper describes the results of our investigations on $MCd(Dtc)_4$ complex, $M=VO(IV)$, $Mn(II)$, $Fe(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$, $Cu(II)$ or $Zn(II)$; Dtc =piperidine dithiocarbamate, diethyldithiocarbamate.

Experimental

All chemicals used were B.D.H.(LR) grade. Sodium salts of piperidine dithiocarbamate and diethyldithiocarbamate were prepared by the known method^{1,10} (Found : C, 32.51; H, 4.69; N, 6.21; S, 29.20. Calcd. for $C_8H_{10}NS_2Na \cdot 2H_2O$; C, 32.86; H, 4.59; N, 6.38; S, 29.24% and Found : C, 25.47; H, 7.45; N, 6.71; S, 28.17. Calcd. for $C_8H_{10}NS_2Na \cdot 3H_2O$; C, 26.66; H, 7.15; N, 6.21; S, 28.46%).

Synthesis of complexes: $Na_2[Cd(pDtc)_4]$ and $Na_2[Cd(Et_2Dtc)_4]$ were prepared *in situ* by gradual addition of $Cd(NO_3)_2$ solution in acetone-water (80 : 20, v/v) to a solution of Na_2Dtc or $NaEt_2Dtc$ in the same solvent mixture in 1 : 4 molar ratio with vigorous stirring. The complexes $MCd(Dtc)_4$ were prepared by gradual addition with constant stirring of a solution of metal nitrate to a solution of $Na_2[Cd(pDtc)_4]$ or $Na_2[Cd(Et_2Dtc)_4]$ prepared *in situ* as described above in 1 : 1 molar ratio in acetone-water (80 : 20, v/v). The complexes thus precipitated were filtered immediately to avoid the formation of $Cd(Dtc)_2$ and washed with

the above solvent mixture and then with ether and dried in vacuum.

$MCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$; $M=VO(IV)$, $Mn(II)$, $Fe(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$, $Cu(II)$

Analysis of the complexes: The complexes were analysed for metals using standard literature procedures¹¹. Sulphur was estimated as $BaSO_4$ and nitrogen microanalytically. The analytical data are given Table 1.

Physical measurements: Molar conductance of the complexes in nitrobenzene at $10^{-6}M$ concentration was measured with WTW conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature on Cahn-Faraday electro balance using $HgCo(NCS)_4$ as calibrant and experimental magnetic susceptibilities were corrected for diamagnetism. Molar conductance and magnetic moment data are included in Table 1. Electronic spectra of Na_2Dtc and $NaEt_2Dtc$ and complexes were recorded on Cary-14 spectrophotometer in nujol while the ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer model-621 in nujol ($4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and in KBr ($4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The absorption bands of diagnostic value and their assignments are given in Table 1. ESR spectra were recorded as chloroform solution both at room and liquid nitrogen temperatures on a Varian X-band spectrometer model E-4 using DPPH as an

* Author to whom all correspondence should be made.

VOcd (pDtc)₄

MCd(pDtc)₄; M=Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) or Zn(II)

TABLE 1.—ANALYTICAL DATA, COLOUR, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURE OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Found (Calcd.)(%)				Molar conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	Decomposition Temperature (°C)
		M	Cd	N	S			
VOcd(pDtc) ₄	Dirty yellow	6.15 (6.20)	14.00 (13.72)	6.70 (6.82)	30.53 (31.26)	0.59	1.74	197*
VOcd(Et ₂ Dtc) ₄	Dirty yellow	6.81 (6.59)	14.12 (14.55)	7.00 (7.37)	32.92 (33.22)	0.58	1.69	182
MnCd(pDtc) ₄	Violet	6.89 (6.79)	13.64 (13.90)	7.17 (6.92)	31.62 (31.66)	0.21	3.85	165
MnCd(Et ₂ Dtc) ₄	Violet	8.82 (9.09)	15.21 (14.78)	7.00 (7.37)	32.50 (33.76)	0.22	4.40	102
FeCd(Et ₂ Dtc) ₄	Dark brown	6.89 (7.33)	15.23 (14.77)	7.01 (7.36)	32.71 (33.70)	0.31	3.80	178
CoCd(pDtc) ₄	Green	7.10 (7.25)	13.60 (13.83)	6.70 (6.89)	31.10 (31.57)	0.30	2.37	280
CoCd(Et ₂ Dtc) ₄	Green	7.39 (7.71)	14.20 (14.71)	6.89 (7.38)	32.78 (33.57)	0.61	2.52	219
NiCd(pDtc) ₄	Olive green	6.70 (7.22)	13.05 (13.83)	6.58 (6.89)	30.90 (31.58)	0.07	diamag.	248
NiCd(Et ₂ Dtc) ₄	Olive green	7.11 (7.68)	13.69 (14.71)	7.20 (7.33)	32.77 (33.58)	0.11	diamag.	204
CuCd(pDtc) ₄	Chocolate	7.55 (7.77)	13.60 (13.75)	6.58 (6.85)	31.45 (31.39)	0.18	1.73	228
CuCd(Et ₂ Dtc) ₄	Chocolate	8.17 (8.25)	14.01 (14.60)	7.31 (7.27)	32.75 (33.32)	0.15	1.70	155
ZnCd(pDtc) ₄	White	7.65 (6.98)	13.80 (13.72)	6.90 (6.84)	31.10 (31.32)	0.07	diamag.	286

* Melting point.

internal reference. The in-plane σ -bonding parameter (α^2) was calculated according to the method¹² of Narayana and Sastry.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data indicate the formation of complexes of general formula $MCd(Dtc)_4$. All the complexes decompose in 102-280° temperature range except $VOCd(pDtc)_4$ which melts at 197°. The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but slightly soluble in nitrobenzene and chloroform. Due to insolubility of the complexes we could neither grow single crystal of the complexes nor determine their molecular weights. Our structural studies were therefore, confined to molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, electronic, esr and ir spectral measurements. The very low molar conductance values indicate the non-electrolytic¹³ nature of the bimetallic tetradi-thiocarbamates.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements: The magnetic moments of oxovanadium(IV) and Cu(II) complexes indicate the presence of one unpaired electron. The μ_{eff} values of Mn(II) complexes are consistent with quartet¹⁴ ($S=3/2$) ground state and eliminate the possibility of any dominant antiferromagnetic type of exchange interaction. The magnetic moments of Fe(II) complex is indicative of low-spin nature of the complex. While Ni(II) complexes are diamagnetic, cobalt(II) complexes have magnetic moments of 2.37 B.M. for $CoCd(pDtc)_4$ and 2.52 B.M. for $CoCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$ showing square planar geometry around Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions¹⁵.

Electronic spectral studies: $VOCd(pDtc)_4$ and $VOCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$ exhibit three bands at 11765, 16000, 22220 cm^{-1} and at 11110, 17390 and 23530 cm^{-1} assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$, d_{xz} , $d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions respectively assuming square pyramidal geometry¹⁶ with C_{2v} symmetry. Two bands observed at 10255 cm^{-1} and 15870 cm^{-1} for $CoCd(pDtc)_4$ and at 10255 cm^{-1} and 15700 cm^{-1} for $CoCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$ are attributed to $d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{yz}$ and $d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{xy}$ transitions in square planar geometry respectively. The band at 10255 cm^{-1} being the most characteristic of square planar¹⁷ geometry may be taken as equal to 15 B from which B works out to 683.7 cm^{-1} for both the complexes. The two d-d transition bands at 16000 cm^{-1} and 21051 cm^{-1} in $NiCd(pDtc)_4$ and $NiCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$ are assigned to d_{xz} , $d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions respectively assuming square planar geometry¹⁸ with D_{4h} symmetry around Ni(II). The orbital parameter¹⁹ Δ_1 was calculated from the first spin-allowed d-d transition band by assuming a correction factor^{20,21} ($F_2=10F_4=800$ cm^{-1}) of 2800 cm^{-1} for Ni^{2+} . The Δ_1 values are the same for both the complexes and place the pDtc and Et_2Dtc in the spectrochemical series of sulphur donors²² as follows: maleonitriledithiolate (14490) < diethyldithiophosphate (17300) < dithioacetylacetone (17690) $\approx$ 1-phenyl-5-methyl-2, 4-dithiobiuret anion (17710)

< dithiomalonamide anion (17950) < ethylxanthate (18300) < dithiobiuret anion (18430) < diethyldithiocarbamate (18800) $\approx$ piperidine dithiocarbamate (18,800) < 2,3-dimercaptopropanol anion (19000) < dithiomalonate (20200) < dithiooxalate (20500). A broad band observed at 22725 cm^{-1} in visible spectrum of $CuCd(pDtc)_4$ and two bands at 14815 cm^{-1} and 22272 cm^{-1} in $CuCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$ are attributed to d-d transition in square planar geometry²³.

ESR spectral studies: The room temperature esr spectrum of $CuCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$ complex in chloroform solution consists of a quartet ($g_{iso}=2.0504$ and $A_{iso}=77.5$ G). While the frozen solution spectrum is consistent with a $(d_{z^2})^1$ ground state²⁴ in as much as it shows the well resolved parallel features, the g-values being in the order: $g_{\parallel}(2.0734) > g_{\perp}(2.0044) \approx g_e(2.0023)$. This rules out the possibility of the presence of $Cu(Et_2Dtc)_2$ in our complex as an amorphous mixture with $Cd(Et_2Dtc)_2$, since $Cu(Et_2Dtc)_2$ has $(d_{x^2-y^2})^1$ ground state as evidenced by its frozen solution²⁵ as well as Zn and Ni diluted single crystal²⁶ esr spectral studies. The in-plane σ -bonding parameter α^2 is found to be 0.717 indicating a considerable covalency in the Cu-S bond. The reversal of ground state in our $CuCd(Et_2Dtc)_4$ is probably due to bridging bidentate behaviour of Dtc ion as compared to its chelating bidentate behaviour in $Cu(Et_2Dtc)_2$. The greater affinity of sulphur for Cd^{2+} as compared to Cu^{2+} causes the weakening of Cu-S bond which is further supported by the increase in α^2 (0.717) value compared to its value 0.5929 in $Cu(Et_2Dtc)_2$ complex.

Infrared spectra: Dithiocarbamate ion may exist in three possible resonating forms:

It has been shown from ir spectral studies that the main contributing structure is (c) in metal dithiocarbamates. This conclusion is based²⁷⁻²⁹ on the fact that $\nu(C=N^+)$ (thioureide band) observed in 1480-1550 cm^{-1} region occurs in between the regions for $\nu(C-N)$ (1250-1350 cm^{-1}) and $\nu(C=S)$ (1640-1690 cm^{-1}). The band observed at 1420-1440 cm^{-1} in ir spectra of Dtc complexes is accordingly assigned^{30,31} to $\nu(C=N^+)$. The C=S stretching frequency³²⁻³⁴ has been used to distinguish between the uni- and bidentate nature of dithiocarbamate group. If Dtc is bidentate, as in $Zn(S_2CNET_2)_2$, a single band at 995 cm^{-1} is observed, whereas a doublet (at 1005, 983 cm^{-1}) is obtained for unidentate Dtc as in EtS_2CNET_2 . The occurrence of a single $\nu(C-S)$ band in 990-1000 cm^{-1} region in all our Dtc complexes, therefore, shows the uninegative bidentate behaviour of Dtc. A strong

band at 970 cm^{-1} is attributed to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ in vanadyl complex. The non-ligand bands occurring at $345\text{--}380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $385\text{--}420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})^{ss}$ and $\nu(\text{Cd}-\text{S})^{ss}$ modes respectively. Based on analytical data and physico-chemical studies, polymeric structure is proposed for bimetallic tetrabisdithiocarbamate complexes.

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